

A P O L L O

D6.7: Validation Report

WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation

Authors: Vangelis ANASTASIOU (AUA), Zisis TSIROPOULOS (AUA), Spyros FOUNTAS (AUA)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

This project is co-funded
by the European Union

A P O L L O

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© **APOLLO Consortium, 2016**

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	687412	Acronym	APOLLO	
Full Title	Advisory platform for small farms based on earth observation			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2015: Bringing EO applications to the market			
Type of Action	Research and innovation Action			
Start Date	1 st March 2016	Duration	34 months	
Project URL	apollo-h2020.eu			
Document URL	-			
EU Project Officer	Iulia Simion			
Project Coordinator	Polimachi Simeonidou			
Deliverable	D6.7: Validation Report			
Work Package	WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M34	Actual	M34
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	DRAXIS Environmental SA			
Lead Author	Vangelis Anastasiou	Email	evangelos_anastasiou@hotmail.gr	
	Agricultural University of Athens	Phone	+302105294035	
Other authors	Zisis Tsiropoulos, Spyros Fountas, Dragutin Protic, Dimitra Perperidou			
Contributions from	DRAXIS, UBFCE, EVF, ACP, UPOR, AGRISAT			
Reviewer(s)	UBFCE			
Keywords	APOLLO Services Validation, APOLLO Services Evaluation, Questionnaire Survey, Interview Survey			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	21/2/2019	Draft	Initial version sent to reviewers	AUA
2.0	22/2/2019	Final	Reviewers comments addressed	AUA

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	7
2	APOLLO products validation.....	7
2.1	Earth Observation products validation	7
2.2	Yield product validation.....	8
3	Pilot implementation.....	10
4	Experiments on APOLLO tillage scheduling and irrigation scheduling evaluation	10
5	Questionnaire and Interview Results.....	11
5.1	Questionnaire Results.....	11
5.1.1	Tillage Scheduling Evaluation	12
5.1.2	Irrigation Scheduling Evaluation.....	13
5.1.3	Crop Growth Monitoring Service Questionnaire Evaluation.....	15
5.1.4	Crop Yield Estimation Service Questionnaire Evaluation	16
5.1.5	APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting	18
5.1.6	APOLLO Management Zoning.....	19
5.1.7	APOLLO Platform	20
5.1.8	Additional comments	21
5.2	Interview Results	21
5.2.1	APOLLO success stories	21
5.2.2	APOLLO advantages	22
5.2.3	APOLLO drawbacks	23
5.2.4	APOLLO selling points.....	23
6	Conclusions	25
7	References	26
8	Annex	27
8.1	Online Questionnaire	27
8.2	Interview Questionnaire	29

Table of Figures

Figure 1	Time difference between harvest date and the date of best yield estimation (the date of best yield is date when system shows the yield as close as the real yield)	9
Figure 2	Frequency of answers on question 4 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	12
Figure 3	Frequency of answers on question 5 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	13
Figure 4	Frequency of answers on question 6 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	13
Figure 5	Frequency of answers on question 7 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	14
Figure 6	Frequency of answers on question 8 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	14
Figure 7	Frequency of answers on question 9 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	15
Figure 8	Frequency of answers on question 10 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	15
Figure 9	Frequency of answers on question 11 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	16
Figure 10	Frequency of answers on question 12 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	16
Figure 11	Frequency of answers on question 13 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	17
Figure 12	Frequency of answers on question 14 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	17
Figure 13	Frequency of answers on question 15 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	18
Figure 14	Frequency of answers on question 16 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	18
Figure 15	Frequency of answers on question 17 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	19
Figure 16	Frequency of answers on question 18 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	19
Figure 17	Frequency of answers on question 19 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	20
Figure 18	Frequency of answers on question 20 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	20
Figure 19	Frequency of answers on question 21 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.	21

Table of Tables

Table 1	Number of Yield measurements collected in each country	8
Table 2	Min, Mean and Max harvest date	8
Table 3	Summary statistics for yield difference, harvest yield - APOLLO yield one month before [t/ha]	8
Table 4	Summary for date differences, best date - harvest date	9
Table 5	Summary statistics for yield difference, harvest yield - APOLLO yield at the best date [t/ha]	9
Table 6	Crops tested in APOLLO project	10
Table 7	Average performance of each APOLLO service at field trials	11
Table 8	Characteristics of the APOLLO end-users who participated in the questionnaire survey per country, age group, education level and crop type.	11

Executive summary

The deliverable at hand – the Validation Report – provides an overview of the whole activities that carried out for evaluation and validation in the course of the APOLLO project at the locations of the three pilot areas and presents results and findings. The Validation Report consists of six chapters:

- In the first chapter, the reasoning for conducting an evaluation survey for achieving user's acceptance is analysed.
- In the second chapter, there is a brief reference to validation results that are used in APOLLO added value services with main focus on the yield product validation.
- The third chapter refers to the use of the APOLLO added value service in terms of crops, area covered and number of APOLLO services users.
- In the fourth chapter, a brief report on the evaluation of added value services is provided and especially for the evaluation results on tillage and irrigation scheduling services.
- The fifth chapter refers to the online questionnaire and interview results on the acceptance of the APOLLO added value services by the alpha and beta users.
- In the sixth and final chapter, there is the conclusion of the overall performance of the APOLLO platform and added value services during the evaluation period of the APOLLO project.

1 Introduction

The main objective of the APOLLO project was to develop a commercial platform that will provide advisory services to small farmers regarding i) tillage scheduling, ii) irrigation scheduling, iii) crop growth monitoring and iv) crop yield estimation. The services are based on Earth Observation Data coming from the EU's Sentinel satellites as well as on free online databases. These data are inserted in state-of-the-art algorithms for providing valuable information to small farmers and crop consultants regarding the aforementioned services. While, two more services were developed in the APOLLO project in order to address end users needs as they were identified during WP2 duration and specifically in user requirements and co-creation tasks. These were the weather forecasting and alert and the management zone services. Main aim of the weather forecasting and alert service was to support end users in scheduling on time their activities by taking into account the weather conditions also. In addition, management zones service was aiming to help them understand better their infield variability and delineate management zones that they can later use for applying variable rate applications through precision agriculture.

The commercial success of APOLLO solution depend highly from its users' acceptance. However, in order to increase its user acceptance, APOLLO needs to convince its users for the benefits that it can provide to them. This was done by following a series of actions that included questionnaire and interview surveys, co-creation sessions and services validation and evaluation.

Questionnaire and interview surveys can help through the identification of important traits and characteristics for adoption of new farming practices (Fountas et al., 2005; Ferrari and Cavallo, 2011; Anastasiou et al., 2017). Moreover, co-creation sessions can help on the proper development and adoption of new methods and services in the agri-food sector (Schneider et al., 2012; Voorberg et al., 2015; Candelo et al., 2018). Finally, validation and evaluation of models and services are important for the overall acceptance and therefore marketability of proposed solutions and services (Basso et al., 2001; Britz et al., 2012)

2 APOLLO products validation

2.1 Earth Observation products validation

To assess the quality of APOLLO EO products, namely soil moisture, LAI and biomass, a validation protocol was defined and followed.

For soil moisture, a validation with respect to in-situ measurements was not possible due to the limited temporal overlap between the StarLab soil-moisture product and the available in-situ measurements. The solution was to estimate the correlation of APOLLO soil moisture and RT1-model that based on a first-order approximation of the radiative transfer model at 100m that works on Sentinel-1 data. High positive correlations are observed in cereal-fields while insignificant or negative correlation values are obtained in fields with garlic or cotton crops. Also, for operational exploitation, removing outliers as a pre-processing step in SM data generation is mandatory and it is preferable to use average per-field SM data in APOLLO services instead of in-field variability.

Cross-validation method used for LAI and biomass, resulted in both models calibrated with in situ data collected in APOLLO project and in estimation of the quality of the products. Final results show that LAI product for wheat, maize, cotton, soya and sugar beet is ready for operational use, while

models for barley and garlic need additional in situ data for further calibration of the models. For biomass, models for wheat, maize, cotton and soya are ready for operational use, while garlic needs to be further calibrated.

The details of the EO products validation procedure and results are presented in deliverable D6.4 Validation report.

2.2 Yield product validation

APOLLO yield product was validated by comparison with in situ data collected on the pilot fields during the project. The yield measured after the harvest from a number of parcels in APOLLO pilot areas was compared with the yield estimated by APOLLO service. The number of reference parcels per crop type and per pilot country is presented in Table 1. The main statistics of the harvest dates per crop for the reference parcels are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Number of Yield measurements collected in each country

Crop_type	Greece	Serbia	Spain	Total
Barley	0	0	9	9
Cotton	27	0	0	27
Maize	0	30	3	33
Soya	0	3	0	3
Sunflower	0	3	0	3
Wheat	6	1	9	16

Table 2 Min, Mean and Max harvest date

Crop_type	n	Min	Mean	Max
Barley	9	2018-06-06	2018-06-20	2018-07-07
Cotton	27	2018-09-19	2018-09-29	2018-10-21
Maize	33	2018-09-17	2018-10-05	2018-12-10
Soya	3	2018-09-17	2018-09-18	2018-09-20
Sunflower	3	2018-08-21	2018-08-22	2018-08-24
Wheat	16	2018-06-20	2018-07-04	2018-07-13

As farmers need yield estimation before harvest, we calculated the accuracy of yield provided by APOLLO service one month before harvest as the main quality parameter. The statistics including accuracy measures RMSE and CV are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Summary statistics for yield difference, harvest yield - APOLLO yield one month before [t/ha]

Crop_type	n	Min	RMSE	Max	CV%
Barley	9	-1.8	3.0	7.9	37.5
Cotton	27	-2.2	0.9	1.2	16.4
Maize	33	-3.0	2.6	6.7	21.7
Soya	3	-2.6	1.6	0.2	45.7
Sunflower	3	1.2	0.6	2.3	13.3
Wheat	16	-2.8	2.6	6.9	28.9

Table 3 - Summary statistics for yield difference, harvest yield - APOLLO yield one month before [t/ha]

In addition, we searched for the dates when the APOLLO yield estimations fit the measured yield best. For each crop, temporal distance between these dates and harvest days were calculated (in days from the harvest day) and statistics is presented in Table 4 and Table 5. The temporal distribution of the dates of best yield estimation is shown in Figure 1. These findings are of great significance for better understanding of the yield estimation model behavior.

Figure 1 Time difference between harvest date and the date of best yield estimation (the date of best yield is date when system shows the yield as close as the real yield)

Table 4 Summary for date differences, best date - harvest date

Crop_type	n	Min	st.dev	Mean	Max
Barley	9	-50 days	16.7 days	-31.8 days	-4 days
Cotton	27	-87 days	16.5 days	-43.2 days	-26 days
Maize	33	-129 days	27.4 days	-39.8 days	-5 days
Soya	3	-70 days	5.5 days	-64.3 days	-59 days
Sunflower	3	-23 days	8.0 days	-15.3 days	-7 days
Wheat	16	-73 days	13.5 days	-46.4 days	-23 days

Table 5 Summary statistics for yield difference, harvest yield - APOLLO yield at the best date [t/ha]

Crop_type	n	Min	RMSE	Max	CV%
Barley	9	-0.4	1.1	2.8	13.8
Cotton	27	-1.9	0.5	0.8	9.1
Maize	33	-0.6	1.9	6.4	15.8
Soya	3	-0.2	0.2	0.2	5.7
Sunflower	3	0.1	0.7	1.5	15.6
Wheat	16	-2.8	2.4	6.9	26.7

The results of the validation protocol show that the models for yield estimation produce good results one month before harvest for cotton, maize, wheat and sunflower. Analysis of the temporal distance between the harvest date and the date when yield estimation was the best, revealed that an earlier yield estimation (more than one month before harvest) would achieve even better accuracy for all the crops except for sunflower.

3 Pilot implementation

The APOLLO platform through its added value services provides information for many different crop types including cereals, legumes, industrial crops, vegetables, fruits and berries, although the initial concept was to provide them only for wheat, maize and cotton cultivation. In total, 13 different crops covering 6,267.71 ha were used for testing purposes from the alpha and beta users of APOLLO in the three pilot sites in Greece, Serbia and Spain. As it is presented in Table 6, cereals covered 4,335.95 ha in total, industrial crops covered 1,484.75 ha in total, legumes 148.73 ha, vegetables 66.39 ha, fruits 121.12 ha and berry crops 110.77 ha. Finally, more than 60 farmers and crop consultants used the APOLLO services during the project duration.

Table 6 Crops tested in APOLLO project

Crop Type	Crop	Area (ha)
Cereals	Wheat	2552.45
	Maize	1481.76
	Barley	301.74
Industrial	Cotton	1248.10
	Sunflower	180.94
	Sugar Beet	55.71
Legumes	Soybean	148.73
Vegetables	Purple Garlic	59.53
	Chinese Garlic	6.86
Fruits	Almonds	119.01
	Olives	2.11
Berries	Winegrapes	110.77

4 Experiments on APOLLO tillage scheduling and irrigation scheduling evaluation

A series of field trials were conducted in the APOLLO pilot sites supervised by ACP, UPOR and AGRISAT. The results of the field trials were presented in D6.6 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report. According to the results APOLLO tillage scheduling service can help farmers achieve up to 32% savings in fuel consumption and increase their productivity by tilling more area in less time. Moreover, APOLLO tillage scheduling service helped producers that followed its advices to achieve the same or higher yields while achieving significant fuel and cost savings on tillage operations. Regarding the performance of APOLLO irrigation scheduling service, up to 11% water savings were

presented in cotton fields while the water savings in Spain were less than 5% on wheat and maize crops. Finally, the crop growth and yield of both APOLLO services (tillage and irrigation scheduling) had almost the same or better performance when compared with the current field practices (Table 7). However, the local weather conditions as well as the operation window of each farming practice mainly affect the performance of APOLLO services. All the aforementioned, indicated that the APOLLO platform can help farmers on achieving a more sustainable and profitable crop production.

Table 7 Average performance of each APOLLO service at field trials

Crop	APOLLO Tillage Scheduling	APOLLO Irrigation Scheduling	Yield
Cotton	-1 %	-10.5 %	-1 %
Wheat	N/A	-3.5 %	-1 %
Maize	-17 %	-5 %	+1 %
Soybean	-12 %	N/A	+20 %

5 Questionnaire and Interview Results

5.1 Questionnaire Results

A questionnaire survey took place on the pilot sites in Greece, Serbia and Spain in order to assess in a qualitative way, the performance of APOLLO services as well as to assess its acceptance after the first evaluation period which results are presented in D6.5 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report. APOLLO project partners that were responsible for the pilot sites in each country (ACP, AgriSat and UPOR) organized the survey with the APOLLO beta testers from each region participating in the survey. The questionnaire consisted of 22 questions that are divided in seven sections. The first section requests information on demographic characteristics, the second section requests general information on type of crops that they used APOLLO platform, the third, fourth, fifth and sixth sections have questions on APOLLO tillage scheduling service, on APOLLO irrigation scheduling service, on APOLLO crop growth monitoring service, on APOLLO crop yield estimation service and on APOLLO platform accordingly. Moreover, the seventh and eighth section asked APOLLO platform end-users about the APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting and the APOLLO management zones services. Finally, the end-users are questioned about the APOLLO platform in the ninth section. The guidelines that were used for the questionnaire survey can be found in the Annex. The characteristics of the APOLLO end-users who participated in the questionnaire survey are presented in the table below (Table 8).

Table 8 Characteristics of the APOLLO end-users who participated in the questionnaire survey per country, age group, education level and crop type.

Question Type	Answers	GREECE	SERBIA	SPAIN
Age Group	18-34	10	6	6
	35-44	6	2	4
	45-54	9	1	-
	55-64	5	-	2
	65+	1	-	1
Education Level	Primary	3	-	-
	Secondary	14	1	6
	Graduate	10	7	5
	Post Graduate	4	1	2

Crop Type	ArableCrops	31	3	4
	Orchards	-	6	6
	OpenFieldVegetables	-	1	3

Based on the table, most of the APOLLO beta testers were below 44 years old (64%), having at least a bachelor degree from a university (54%) and cultivating arable crops (72%). The APOLLO beta testers sample indicated that most of the farmers were experienced on using technology due to their young age, while their higher education level helped them to understand better the information that was provided by the APOLLO services. Although, most of the beta farmers were cultivating arable crops which are commonly used on satellite applications for agriculture, they were willing to test the platform to other crops like orchard crops and open field vegetables. It needs to be highlighted that most of APOLLO beta testers (farmers and agronomists) were using smart agriculture services for the first time in their life through APOLLO platform.

In the subsections below, the frequency of answers on each question are presented and analyzed.

5.1.1 Tillage Scheduling Evaluation

Most of the farmers found that the APOLLO tillage scheduling service is not difficult to use (34%) while 43% stated that it is easy to use (Figure 2). This can be explained by the fact that most of the farmers were young (<44 years old) and had higher education while researchers have identified that sociodemographic factors affect greatly use and adoption of new technologies in agriculture (Pierpaoli et al., 2013). In Addition, more than 75% of the beta testers of the APOLLO tillage scheduling service stated that tillage scheduling service was useful to them (Figure 3). It is worth mentioning that the Spanish farmers apply minimum or no-till practices that result in decreased number of tillage operations per year and consequently did limited use of the APOLLO tillage scheduling service. As it is presented in Figure 4, more than 55% of the APOLLO end-users stated that they are going to use the service in their tillage operations while a 17% of the farmers stated that they will not use it. This is explained by the fact that Spanish farmers are using minimum or no-till practices which have low needs in number of tillage operations and consequently do not have high needs on having this type of information.

Figure 2 Frequency of answers on question 4 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q5. Do you find APOLLO tillage scheduling service useful or not useful?

Figure 3 Frequency of answers on question 5 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q6. Will you use the service in your tillage operations?

Figure 4 Frequency of answers on question 6 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.2 Irrigation Scheduling Evaluation

Most of the farmers found that the APOLLO irrigation scheduling service is not difficult to use (42%) while 34% stated that it is easy or very easy to use (Figure 5), while only 15% of the beta testers found it difficult or somewhat difficult to use. In addition, almost 80% of the users found that APOLLO irrigation service provides adequate usefulness (Figure 6). It needs to be highlighted that not all farmers are irrigating their crops. Especially in Serbia they do not apply irrigation in any crop. However, the use of irrigation products helped them to understand not only when to irrigate but also how soil moisture affects them in final yield. Finally, most beta testers (55%) stated that they will use the APOLLO irrigation service in their irrigation operation since this service helped them to understand better the impact of soil moisture on their operations (Figure 7).

Q7. Do you find APOLLO irrigation scheduling service easy or difficult to use?

Figure 5 Frequency of answers on question 7 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q8. Do you find APOLLO irrigation scheduling service useful or not useful?

Figure 6 Frequency of answers on question 8 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q9. Will you use the service in your irrigation operations?

Figure 7 Frequency of answers on question 9 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.3 Crop Growth Monitoring Service Questionnaire Evaluation

Most of the beta users (80%) did not face any difficulties using the APOLLO crop growth monitoring service as it is presented in Figure 8. This was justified by the fact that most of the beta testers were young in age, they were most used on using personal computers, and web based applications as well as smartphones. Also, a huge percent (79%) of APOLLO beta testers found that APOLLO crop growth monitoring service is useful for their practices. This was justified by the fact that all beta users know that crop growth monitoring is one of the most activities that take place during a crop season (Figure 9). Moreover, most APOLLO beta users stated that they will incorporate APOLLO crop growth monitoring service on their crop scouting activities after identifying the benefits that this service provided to them (Figure 10).

Q10. Do you find APOLLO crop growth monitoring service easy or difficult to use?

Figure 8 Frequency of answers on question 10 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q11. Do you find APOLLO crop growth monitoring useful or not useful?

Figure 9 Frequency of answers on question 11 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q12. Will you use the service in your crop growth monitoring operations?

Figure 10 Frequency of answers on question 12 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.4 Crop Yield Estimation Service Questionnaire Evaluation

Regarding the easiness of using the APOLLO crop yield estimation service, 17% of the beta users stated that it was very easy to use, 32% answered that it was somewhat easy while the rest answered either that it was somewhat difficult or neither easy and difficult (11 % and 40% accordingly) (Figure 11). Additionally, most APOLLO beta users (58%) found the service to be useful for their farming operations (Figure 12). Regarding the willingness of the APOLLO beta testers to use the crop yield estimation service, most of them stated that they probably will use it (32%), while 23% of them answered that they will definitely use them in the future (Figure 13).

Q13. Do you find APOLLO crop yield estimation easy or difficult to use?

Figure 11 Frequency of answers on question 13 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q14. Do you find APOLLO crop yield estimation useful or not useful?

Figure 12 Frequency of answers on question 14 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q15. Will you use the service for your crop yield estimation?

Figure 13 Frequency of answers on question 15 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.5 APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting

Most of the farmers (43 %) answered that APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting was very easy to use it while 28 % found it somewhat easy (Figure 14). In addition, most of the farmers (89 %) answered that APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting was very useful or useful to use it while only 11 % gave another answer (Figure 15). This is because both groups (farmers and agronomists) understood how valuable this information in agriculture is.

Q16. Do you find APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting easy or difficult to use?

Figure 14 Frequency of answers on question 16 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q17. Do you find APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting useful or not useful?

Figure 15 Frequency of answers on question 17 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.6 APOLLO Management Zoning

Only 43% of the beta users answered that APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting was either very easy or somewhat easy to use. While 21 % answered that they faced difficulty with the rest of the beta users (34%) stating that it was not easy or difficult to use the service (Figure 16). While, only 47 % of the beta users answered that APOLLO management zones was very useful or useful to use it while only 2 % did not find any use (Figure 17).

Q18. Do you find APOLLO management zones service easy or difficult to use?

Figure 16 Frequency of answers on question 18 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q19. Do you find APOLLO management zones service useful or not useful?

Figure 17 Frequency of answers on question 19 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.7 APOLLO Platform

Only 19% of the APOLLO beta users stated was very easy to use, while the 36% answered that it was somewhat easy to use (Figure 18). From the abovementioned, it is clear that most of the beta users found that the APOLLO platform is easy to use. In addition, most of the beta users (74%) stated that they are going to recommend APOLLO/FARMORE to a friend (Figure 19).

Q20. Was it easy to learn to use APOLLO/FARMORE?

Figure 18 Frequency of answers on question 20 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

Q21. Will you recommend APOLLO/FARMORE to a friend?

Figure 19 Frequency of answers on question 21 of the APOLLO questionnaire on beta users.

5.1.8 Additional comments

Finally, APOLLO beta users commented on additional things that they expect from the APOLLO platform and services to be developed. These were i) support of all APOLLO services to orchards and other crops; ii) on time and precise alerts and notifications using simpler visualization and instructions; iii) more detailed information and maps; iv) add more weather parameters like precipitation and air humidity; and v) stay free.

5.2 Interview Results

An interview survey was held with the APOLLO alpha users in the premises of APOLLO partners in pilot areas. ACP, UPOR and AGRISAT were responsible for the conducting the interviews with farmers that were using the APOLLO platform and services during APOLLO project. Specifically, 18 farmers and agronomists participated in total from which 5 were from Greece, 5 were from Serbia and 8 from Spain. The guidelines of the interview survey are presented in, while the answers on the interview survey are summarized and presented in the following sections.

5.2.1 APOLLO success stories

Most of the farmers experienced benefits regarding cost savings due to decreased fuel and water consumption. While many farmers had better scheduling of their operations due to the better crop growth monitoring that APOLLO offered to them. Specifically, the Greek farmers stated that APOLLO platform was presenting the real picture of their field. While, during tillage they referred to cost savings due to higher tillage speed and lower labor time and fuel consumption. The same thing was stated for the irrigation, in which they found important cost savings due to less water application and time of operation.

Regarding the Serbian farmers, the alpha users (4 farmers) who measured fuel consumption when following APOLLO tillage service experienced in important fuel savings reaching up to 40% less fuel consumptions (2.1 l/ha). Moreover, one farmer stated that he will invest on buying precision farming technologies. His decision was based on availability of affordable maps generated through APOLLO services that can be used as input for precision farming applications such as the management zone and crop growth monitoring maps. He stated that he was looking before for investing on precision

farming technologies but the market has been offering maps based on drone or aerial imagery which are an expensive solution for a small/medium farmer.

Finally in Spain, some farmers stated that APOLLO platform has been their first contact between farmers and the remote sensing data to monitor and manage their crops. While crop growth monitoring service has provided useful information to them and it was interesting to observe their plots and to have information at different spatial and temporal scale, while they stated that some features (e.g. soil moisture level) can be used for scheduling other farming operations like fertilization and spraying.

As it is clear from the above, all users from the three countries had recognized the value of the APOLLO services and the integration of the advices in their farming operations. The usefulness of each service depends on the number and type of farming operations.

5.2.2 APOLLO advantages

Regarding the APOLLO advantages, the Greek users referred to the easy access to the application, registration and registration of parcels without delays and bugs during navigation. One farmer referred that a general overview of moisture on his farm plots helped him to plan the work with the help of the weekly weather forecast. Moreover, the irrigation service helped the majority of producers to take decisions regarding the application of water or not to their crops. Finally, the coloring and categorization of each APOLLO service product values were accepted by the majority of producers, because it was giving them a clear picture.

The Serbian users stated that the services are easy to use, while the APOLLO was perceived as not complicated application, with logical interface and comfortable colors. Moreover, the information is presented in a good way, using bright and logical color schemes for the map data and effective colors for advices (tillage, irrigation). In the same way, advices were perceived as simple and clear. Farmers liked minimalism in the presentation of information, they have even preferred to receive the short report on e-mail every day rather than to check their APOLLO account often. In addition, the information on management zones and time series of crop growing status, as well as possibility to look at historical data was rated by the interviewees as highly useful. They said that they can learn from the data and compare with their own experience and improve the practice. Regarding the advantages related to the quality of APOLLO system, Serbian users identified that i) the instant and easy registration, since in this way the users are not dependent on support from resellers; and ii) the mobile application is an advantage as many farmers prefer smart phones (which they use often) than desktop/laptop computers. Finally, Serbian users stated that the data provided through APOLLO are considered of a good quality and they were in accordance to the farmers' experience.

Finally, the Spanish users recognized as advantages that APOLLO offers i) quick and easy information consultation on several parameters; ii) irrigation scheduling and forecast; iii) tillage service (including soil moisture) and weather forecast in order to work more efficiently; iv) yield estimation service during crop growth; v) tillage scheduling service that can help them schedule other operations also (e.g. fertilizer application, sowing); vi) crop monitoring that can help them observe their fields at once; and vii) easy to use mobile app (FARMORE) and includes the weather forecast and tillage scheduling services also.

From the above mentioned, all users have clearly identified as an advantage the simple and easy way of use of APOLLO, while the services helped them to increase their efficiency and profitability. Finally, some farmers indicated that some products of the APOLLO services could be used in other operations also while some farmers have clearly understood that APOLLO can help them move to more advanced cultivation practices (e.g. precision agriculture).

5.2.3 APOLLO drawbacks

Regarding APOLLO drawbacks, the Greek users indicated that it was confusing for them to understand if there was rainfall in the field area or not due to the spatial variability of the weather and that needs further investigation. They also stated that this may lead to insecurity and hesitation on taking decisions. Moreover, they want to have as simpler suggestions and classification as possible because in some cases they are feeling confused.

Regarding the Serbia users, a drawback was considered the low level of e-literacy that didn't allow farmers to exploit full potential of APOLLO platform. Thus, a number of potential users would prefer to either receive the information from APOLLO through a consultant, or to receive advices through e-mail (daily report). In addition, they stated that precise identification of parcel's location and digitization of parcel boundaries was sometimes a challenge to them due to the outdated very high imagery and updated Sentinel-2 natural color composite with reduced spatial resolution. They stated that they wanted to use the GPS coordinates of the parcel because the farmers reported that the size of the parcel calculated by APOLLO platform didn't fit precisely to the real measures. Moreover, the Serbian users stated that they would prefer to have a joint map of all their parcels with basic APOLLO info so they can plan activities more easily (e.g. joint map showing conditions for tillage (with parcels colored according to the soil workability level) would facilitate optimal decision process on the work schedule).

Finally, the Spanish users stated that i) registration of the plot into the platform is slow; ii) irrigation dose wasn't adjusted to real crop water demand compared with other resources that use advanced information (e.g. IoT systems); iii) there were differences in yield estimation data when compared to real values; iv) the accuracy of the services needs to be increased; v) in some cases the farmers did not understand well the provided and needed further clarification that needs to be include in the user's guide; vi) it was very time consuming for the farmers who had many parcels weren't comfortable with the process of monitoring their fields; vii) they were feeling uncomfortable when they were changing the crop type and the date of harvest and sowing of a parcel; and viii) a button to edit the parcel should be in the dashboard. Regarding the mobile app they stated that i) the app needs to have maps and that the irrigation dose needs to be included; and ii) they wanted to consult the information they provide whether their field was irrigated or not.

The common drawback that users identified was that it wasn't very clear to them when the data were integrated to the services, while some of them asked about additional features (e.g. joint map and maps on the mobile app).

5.2.4 APOLLO selling points

Regarding the selling points, the Greek users stated that the tillage scheduling service can help farmers to better schedule their operations and achieve a great financial benefit. Moreover, the irrigation scheduling service can help them achieve lower irrigation costs due to decreased number and doses of irrigations. While, the historical data collected by the application can help farmers avoid any mistakes in the future.

Serbian users stated that APOLLO solution "would be" their primary choice since it offers added-value services in a form of simple advices, ease of use and potentially low price. The referred to the only competitive platform existing in the Serbian market (named Agrosens) which also uses satellite data for information on the crops' status, but the application is highly limited to vegetation indices only providing no added-value information or advices to farmers. They identified that the only advantage of Agrosens over APOLLO is the access to official cadastral data, which facilitates parcel identification. Moreover, the Serbian users stated that besides of savings in fuel, water and time that can be a result of using APOLLO, APOLLO can be very useful in improving planning of agriculture

activities by having better sight on the wider picture of their farm (seeing APOLLO account as their virtual farm) and by making decisions supported by quantitative data. Finally, APOLLO exported maps that provide information on in-parcel-variability of a parameter (e.g. management zones, crop growth status, irrigation dose, soil workability) are very valuable as inputs for precision agriculture on annual crops (other than fruits and vegetables where very high spatial resolution is required) and much cheaper alternative to traditional solutions (e.g. drone imagery). They concluded that this could highly encourage the farmers to invest in precision farming tools along subscribing to APOLLO/FARMORE.

Finally, the Spanish users recognized that APOLLO as a solution has great potential. While another selling point is that Apollo puts remote sensing information in the hands of the farmers in a simple way. NDVI and evapotranspiration products can be strong points to pay for APOLLO. Moreover, the farmers stated that they would pay for having a solution like that if it provides reliable and accurate data to them.

All APOLLO users identified the existence of added value services as the main selling point of APOLLO solution and the great commercial potential that a solution like that has because it can help them achieve savings in crop inputs and increase their farm profitability. While, some of them indicated the APOLLO solution as an entry level solution for moving to advanced farming practices (e.g. precision agriculture).

6 Conclusions

Main goal of APOLLO project was to develop a holistic solution for farmers by farmers. The agile process that it was followed during the whole duration of the project, put farmers and crop consultants in the center. In any step of APOLLO's platform and services development there was continuous feedback from its end users in order to develop, validate and evaluate properly a holistic solution that will help farmers and crop consultants during their daily farming operations. Moreover, the APOLLO platform and its components were developed in order to address their needs not only to current farming operations, but to their future ones also. The modular design of APOLLO solution permits further development by enhancing already developed components and/or by adding new ones in order to cover other specific needs (e.g. orchard support, prescription maps for variable rate applications).

In this deliverable, a summary of all actions that took place during APOLLO project for evaluation of APOLLO solution were presented. According to the findings of all actions, the APOLLO services presented significant savings of fuel and water during tillage and irrigation operations while the same or higher yield was achieved. Moreover, the APOLLO platform allowed farmers and crop consultants to monitor and organize better their activities due to the better monitoring that it was provided through the APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting service and the crop growth monitoring service. Furthermore, crop yield estimation service of APOLLO allowed farmers to better organize their harvest activities. Finally, the APOLLO management zones can help farmers and crop consultants to understand better the in field variability and to help in the transition from conventional to precision agriculture practices. All the aforementioned benefits were recognized by the alpha and beta users of the APOLLO platform and services, which lead to their overall acceptance. These users had many stories to tell on how APOLLO platform and its provided services helped them to overcome farming problems that they were facing before.

From all the aforementioned, it is clear that the end users identified that the system performance was very good while they were having some concerns regarding the quality of the data that were provided by APOLLO. The users identified the clear benefits that APOLLO offers to them through the field trials. Moreover, the APOLLO was perceived as easy of use in general from the users however they need to develop more digital skills to get the full benefit. All the aforementioned features of APOLLO were very appreciated by the users, who were very satisfied in general by the performance of APOLLO platform and services and clearly understood the usefulness of APOLLO. Based on that, the users were willing to pay for a solution like that since they clearly perceived the high added value that APOLLO can offer to their current operations by improving them and consequently making their business more profitable.

Finally, APOLLO project developed a promising solution that can work as a paradigm shift that farmers and the agriculture stakeholders in general can use in order to move from conventional ways of farming to more sustainable and efficient ones like smart farming and precision agriculture.

7 References

- Anastasiou, E., Tsiropoulos, Z., Fountas, S., Osann, A., Protic, D., Simeonidou, M., Xenidis, L., 2017. User requirements for a satellite-based advisory platform. *Advances in Animal Biosciences* 8, 368–371. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2040470017000942>
- Basso, B., Ritchie, J.T., Pierce, F.J., Braga, R.P., Jones, J.W., 2001. Spatial validation of crop models for precision agriculture. *Agricultural Systems* 68, 97–112. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-521X\(00\)00063-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-521X(00)00063-9)
- Britz, W., van Ittersum, M. K., Oude Lansink, A. G., &Heckelei, T. (2012). Tools for integrated assessment in agriculture. State of the art and challenges. *Bio-based and Applied Economics Journal*, 1(1050-2016-85718), 125.
- Candelo, E., Casalegno, C., Civera, C., Mosca, F., 2018. Turning Farmers into Business Partners through Value Co-Creation Projects. Insights from the Coffee Supply Chain. *Sustainability* 10, 1018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10041018>
- Ferrari, E., Cavallo, E., n.d. Issues in New Technology Adoption in Agriculture: a Survey Among Italian Tractor's Users 8.
- Fountas, S., Blackmore, S., Ess, D., Hawkins, S., Blumhoff, G., Lowenberg-Deboer, J., Sorensen, C.G., 2005. Farmer Experience with Precision Agriculture in Denmark and the US Eastern Corn Belt. *Precision Agriculture* 6, 121–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11119-004-1030-z>
- Pierpaoli, E., Carli, G., Pignatti, E., Canavari, M., 2013. Drivers of Precision Agriculture Technologies Adoption: A Literature Review. *Procedia Technology* 8, 61–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.protcy.2013.11.010>
- Schneider, F., Steiger, D., Ledermann, T., Fry, P., Rist, S., 2012. No-tillage farming: co-creation of innovation through network building. *Land Degradation & Development* 23, 242–255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.1073>
- Voorberg, W.H., Bekkers, V.J.J.M., Tummers, L.G., 2015. A Systematic Review of Co-Creation and Co-Production: Embarking on the social innovation journey. *PublicManagement Review* 17, 1333–1357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2014.930505>

8 Annex

8.1 Online Questionnaire

To improve APOLLO/FARMORE, we would like to know about your experience using our services. We kindly ask for a few minutes of your time to fill in this survey.

Demographics					
Q1	How old are you?				
	18-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q2	What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?				
	Primary	Secondary	Graduate	Post Graduate	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

General Information			
Q3	For which types of crops have you used APOLLO? (please select all options that apply)		
	Arable Crops	Orchards	Open Field Vegetables
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Tillage Scheduling Service					
Q4	Do you find APOLLO tillage scheduling service easy or difficult to use?				
	Difficult	Somewhat Difficult	Neither Easy nor Difficult	Somewhat Easy	Very Easy
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q5	Do you find APOLLO tillage scheduling service useful or not useful?				
	Not at all Useful	Slightly Useful	Somewhat Useful	Useful	Very Useful
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q6	Will you use the service in your tillage operations?				
	Definitely will not	Probably will not	Might or might not	Probably will	Definitely will
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Irrigation Scheduling Service					
Q7	Do you find APOLLO irrigation scheduling service easy or difficult to use?				

	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasy nor Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q8	Do you find APOLLO irrigation scheduling service useful or not useful?				
	Not at all Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Slightly Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q9	Will you use the service in your irrigation operations?				
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>
Crop Growth Monitoring Service					
Q10	Do you find APOLLO crop growth monitoring service easy or difficult to use?				
	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasy nor Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q11	Do you find APOLLO crop growth monitoring useful or not useful?				
	Not at all Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Slightly Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q12	Will you use the service in your crop growth monitoring operations?				
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>
Crop Yield Estimation Service					
Q13	Do you find APOLLO crop yield estimation easy or difficult to use?				
	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasy nor Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q14	Do you find APOLLO crop yield estimation useful or not useful?				
	Not at all Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Slightly Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q15	Will you use the service for your crop yield estimation?				
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>
APOLLO Weather Forecasting and Alerting					
	Do you find APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting easy or difficult to use?				

Q1 6	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasyorDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q1 7	Do you find APOLLO weather forecasting and alerting useful or not useful?				
	NotatallUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	SlightlyUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryUseful <input type="checkbox"/>
APOLLO ManagementZones					
Q1 8	Do you find APOLLO management zones service easy or difficult to use?				
	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasyorDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q1 9	Do you find APOLLO management zones service useful or not useful?				
	NotatallUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	SlightlyUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatUseful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryUseful <input type="checkbox"/>
APOLLO Platform					
Q2 0	Was it easy to learn to use APOLLO/FARMORE?				
	Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	NeitherEasyorDifficult <input type="checkbox"/>	SomewhatEasy <input type="checkbox"/>	VeryEasy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q2 1	Will you recommend APOLLO/FARMORE to a friend?				
	Definitelywillnot <input type="checkbox"/>	Probablywillnot <input type="checkbox"/>	Mightormightnot <input type="checkbox"/>	Probablywill <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitelywill <input type="checkbox"/>
Q2 2	What can we do to make APOLLO/FARMORE better for you?				

Thank you very much for sharing your opinion with us!!!

8.2 Interview Questionnaire

INSTRUCTIONS FOR FINAL APOLLO INTERVIEWS

Organize the interviews with the farmers and consultants that have got solid experience with using APOLLO during the pilot process (that would probably be the alpha users, but you don't have to be limited to this group).

The interview should consist of three parts: exercise, discussion and conclusions. The conclusions should be summarized and provided back in the Report form presented at the end of the document.

1.Exercise: For each of the farmer to be interviewed chose at least 1 of his parcels registered in APOLLO in 2018. Go together with the farmer through the data provided by APOLLO services for the parcel(s) during this crop season and analyze it. Compare it with what was happening in the field. Ask the farmer to interpret the information.

2.Discussion: Talk with the farmers about their experience with APOLLO. Use questions to manage the conversation. If a question ends with yes/no answer, ask why... Try to find out any difficulties they experienced using APOLLO, the ways APOLLO could bring them benefits, what they liked and didn't like and why, why would they use and pay for APOLLO services, etc.

Try to identify success stories of how APOLLO proved to be useful to farmers during the pilot process.

Try to minimize bias (as alpha users may be advanced and not typical farmers) by asking them to assess also a common farmer's (colleague farmers from the pilot area) attitude, interest, ability...

If similar services exist in the pilot area, ask the interviewees to compare them with APOLLO.

Address and discuss all **three aspects** of APOLLO: 1) system- accessibility through internet (instant registration, no intermediaries..), performance (reliability of the system, speed, bugs..); 2) data – the quality of information and advices received from the services; 3) services - the concept, type of information and advices provided by the services, the way the information and advices are presented (maps, graphs, numbers, colors), managing the account and the parcels, etc.

Let them open up and express their feelings about APOLLO!

3.Conclusions: During the exercise and discussion take notes or record the conversation. After the interview, summarize the conclusions and provide report from your pilot in the following form:

REPORT ON INTERVIEWS

Names of the farmers interviewed

Success stories (describe success stories where APOLLO proved useful to farmers during pilot phase)

Advantages of APOLLO (Please summarize the aspects of APOLLO platform, data and services that are prized or positively perceived by the end users. Indicate if there are disagreements between interviewees.)

Drawbacks of APOLLO (Please summarize the aspects of APOLLO platform, data and services that are identified as potential obstacles for APOLLO market penetration. Indicate if there are disagreements between interviewees)

Selling points of APOLLO (Please try to identify through the interview what makes the APOLLO attractive to customers - why would they pay for APOLLO services. Indicate if there are disagreements between interviewees)

END OF DOCUMENT

This project is co-funded
by the European Union

A P O L L O